

Magnetic Room Temperature Refrigeration Using Stacks of Gadolinium Plates

Kasper Wigh Lipsø, s062075@student.dtu.dk

Supervisors: Kasper Kirstein Nielsen, Christian Bahl & Luise Theil Kuhn

Risø National Laboratory for Sustainable Energy

Fuel Cells and Solid State Chemistry Division

Motivation

World electricity consumption

20-40% higher energy efficiency

Reversible process: Airconditioning possible

No toxic greenhouse gasses

The Active Refrigeration Device

The device produce cooling through a four step regenerator cycle. This cycle is illustrated and documented below:

Thermodynamics of the magneto caloric effect

$$\Delta T_{ad} = -\mu_0 \int_{H_1}^{H_2} \frac{T}{C_{H,p}} \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial T} \right)_H dH$$

1) the magnetocaloric material is magnetized, thus decreasing the entropy and thereby increasing the temperature of the material.

2) the water is pushed to the hot end of the device.

3) the magnetocaloric material is demagnetized, decreasing the temperature.

4) the water is pushed to the cold end of the AMR.

Plate geometry -Demagnetization

Plates arranged parallel to the magnetic field

Plates arranged orthogonal to the magnetic field

Perspectives

Magnetic Refrigeration prototypes in the world

Prototype at Risø expected running in March 2011

Risø DTU
National Laboratory for Sustainable Energy